

Towards Motion Measurements of the Human Organ of Corti using Optical Coherence Tomography (OCT)

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Abstract. The “bridge” is a soft tissue structure found in the human cochlear partition between the bony osseous spiral lamina (OSL) and the foot of the inner-pillar cells of the organ of Corti. The bridge and OSL motion may have a profound impact on the overall organ of Corti motion affecting transduction-related relative motion between the reticular lamina (RL) and the tectorial membrane (TM). We imaged through the intact round window membrane with optical coherence tomography (OCT) to visualize and measure the motion of cochlear structures including the basilar membrane (BM), OSL, bridge, RL, and TM. Such measurements can reveal how the bridge and OSL motion may affect motion of structures close to the transduction mechanism.

INTRODUCTION

Studies have shown that the basal cochlear partition cross-sectional anatomy and motion are similar across species of laboratory animals [1-3]. A “*classic view*” of cochlear mechanics emerged from these observations, which was thought to be generalizable across mammals. However, the anatomy of the human cochlear partition differs substantively from the *classic view* [4, 5] and its consequences to mechanics warrants further investigation.

Considering the basal cochlear partition in the *classic view*, the basilar membrane (**BM**) is the dominant mobile region. The medial end of the BM attaches to the bony osseous spiral lamina (**OSL**) and the lateral end to the spiral ligament. However, in humans there is a soft tissue “bridge” between the OSL and BM (Fig. 1B). The organ of Corti is attached to the BM (not the bridge), and within the organ of Corti, the foot of the inner pillar cell is at the bridge-BM junction. The bridge and BM have continuous collagen fibers coursing through them, indicating that they have similar mechanics [4, 5].

Because of the bridge-BM structure, human organ of Corti motion may not undergo the motion previously described with the *classic view*, which has mostly rotational motion at the foot of the inner pillar cell. Instead, the foot of the inner pillar cell in human may both rotate and translate along with the bridge-BM junction. Additionally, the portion of the limbus connected to the bridge as well as the attachment point of the tectorial membrane (**TM**) to the limbus may also have rotational and translational motion. In essence, compared to the *classic view*, the motion of the human cochlear partition structures are far more complex, and such differences are hypothesized to affect transduction-related relative motion between the reticular lamina (**RL**) and TM. Thus, the mechanical mechanism leading to sound transduction in the human cochlea is likely different from the *classic view*. To test this hypothesis, vibration measurements near the RL and TM as a function of radial position and frequency are needed. In the present study, we imaged through the intact round window with optical coherence tomography (**OCT**) to visualize and

measure motion at the tympanic surface and structures within the organ of Corti and the TM to determine their relative motions.

METHODS

Temporal bones were obtained from donors with consent at Massachusetts General Hospital, and experiments were performed at Massachusetts Eye and Ear. Approval for this work was provided by Massachusetts General Brigham (IRB #2020P000508 and #2022P001102). The specimens were prepared similarly to previous studies [5, 7]. All measurements began within 10-30 hours postmortem (5 specimens from 31-89 year old donors). The specimens were cooled to approximately 18° C throughout the experiment by having ice in the sound isolation chamber booth and refrigerated saline below the specimen. The middle-ear cavity was kept moist with saline-saturated Gelfoam pieces tucked in regions of the middle-ear cavity in a manner that did not obscure the imaging view or affect middle-ear motion.

OCT imaging and vibrometry measurements were made with a Spectral Domain OCT system (GAN620C1, Thorlabs, Germany) with 900-nm center wavelength, an A-line scan-camera frame rate of 46-kHz, with 2.2 μm axial resolution (in water) and $\sim 8 \mu\text{m}$ lateral resolution (36 mm, 0.055NA, 2x objective lens). Commercially available software (ThorImage OCT 5.4.8) was used to collect cross-sectional B-scan images of the basal cochlear partition. The specimen was oriented to have a cross-sectional image of the organ of Corti with the BM aligned horizontally, minimal radial width, and maximum height. Custom LABVIEW-based software (VibOCT versions 2.1.5 – 2.1.9) recorded images and made vibration measurements. SyncAv (v0.47) generated pure-tone sequences from 0.1-21 kHz equalized for constant SPLs of ~ 80 -110 dB in the ear canal. Transverse displacement (almost perpendicular to the BM) for 1024 points along A-lines at 20-26 radial locations were measured in response to ear canal sound stimuli.

Stapes velocity was measured with a laser Doppler vibrometer, and after converting to displacement, was used as a reference for cochlear input. Measurements are reported as ratios in dB of cochlear partition point displacement to stapes displacement. The reported vibrometry data were at least 6 dB above the measured noise floor, resulting in reliable displacement measurements above 0.1-0.4 nm. Vibrometry data presented are above 4 kHz, where potential artifacts due to round window motion are negligible [8].

RESULTS

FIGURE 1. Cochlear partition motion with respect to frequency: (A) OCT B-scan image with radial locations of measurements. The OCT beam is shining through the intact round window from below onto the tympanic surface of the partition. (B) Illustration detailing cochlear anatomy and structures of interest. This illustration was derived from a B-scan of a different specimen that had comparable histology available. Abbreviations: Osseous spiral lamina (OSL), bridge (BRI), basilar membrane (BM), inner spiral sulcus (ISS), tectorial membrane (TM), hair cells (HCs), Deiters cells (DCs), pillar cells (PCs), and spiral ligament (SL). (C-D) Frequency responses of magnitude (C) and phase (D) displacements of different radial locations referenced to stapes displacement. Characteristic frequency (CF) was near 13 kHz.

Figure 1A shows an OCT B-scan image of a representative cochlear partition measured 13 hours postmortem. The bright orange and yellow colors are indicative of high reflectivity from the OCT light source. The OCT light passed through the round window to the cochlear partition (from the bottom to top of the image shown in Fig. 1A). Due to its high density, the bony OSL generally had high reflectivity, and as a result the OSL shadowed much of the limbus that was above it. The OSL-bridge junction could be identified by the bridge's low reflectivity and lack of shadowing artifacts in the limbus. Towards the direction of the spiral ligament, the bridge-BM junction was identified by the intersection of the angle between the bridge and BM. Figure 1B is an illustration that shows the estimated locations of cochlear partition structures. This illustration was generated from an OCT image of a different specimen that had comparable histology available. There were variations in appearance of the cochlear partition across ears that might be related to the health of the cochlea (not shown). Unlike the representative ear shown (Fig. 1A), two ears had small (or no) organs of Corti, and the TM was not near the RL region.

Figures 1C-D show the displacement magnitude and phase as a function of frequency at various radial locations of the tympanic surface of the cochlear partition referenced to stapes displacement. The different colored lines in Fig. 1C-D correspond to the locations demarcated by the vertical lines in Fig. 1A. The frequency response of the BM surface exhibited a characteristic frequency (CF) around 13 kHz with maximum magnitude and phase transition consistent with a traveling wave (Fig. 1C-D). Other points along the scala tympani surface also showed similar frequency responses but with lower magnitudes, similar to data presented by Rauffer et al. [5].

FIGURE 2. Motion of cochlear structures at characteristic frequency vs. position: (A) OCT B-scan image and measurement locations of vibrometry data plotted in 2B-C (color-coded by “layers”). (B) Magnitude displacement as a function of radial location. A radial location of $X=0$ corresponds to the bridge-BM junction. (C) Phase displacement as a function of radial location. All vibrometry displacement is normalized by stapes displacement.

Figure 2A shows the locations of single point displacements extracted from the A-line measurements superimposed over the same OCT image (Fig. 1A). These measurement locations are indicated by markers, along three “layers” along the cochlear partition. Different layers are designated with different marker colors and shapes. The blue-square markers in layer 1 are along the scala tympani surface consisting of the OS, bridge, and BM. Layer 2 with orange triangles shows points along the RL, whereas layer 3 is denoted by red circles and are points in the TM. Figure 2B-C plots the displacement magnitude and phase at CF of points along the three layers relative to the stapes displacement, as a function of radial location. The x-axis scale was referenced to the bridge-BM junction, indicated by the vertical dashed line at $0 \mu\text{m}$. A second vertical dashed line indicates the OS-bridge junction about $65 \mu\text{m}$ away from the bridge-BM junction.

The layer 1 displacement magnitude (blue) at the OS was approximately flat at around 12 dB almost to the OS-bridge junction. The motion increased to about 22 dB at the bridge-BM junction and continued to increase at the BM

reaching a peak of about 32 dB. This location of maximum magnitude was estimated to be near the foot of the outer-pillar cell (PCs illustrated in Fig. 1B). Beyond the peak towards the spiral ligament, the BM motion decreased down to about 12 dB. The layer 2 motion magnitude (orange) at the RL was approximately 4 dB lower than the BM magnitude. The layer 3 magnitude (red) of the TM was similar to the BM magnitude. Overall, there is little variation in phase (<0.1 cycles) across radial location for each layer, but there were changes in phase that occurred near the OSL-bridge and bridge-BM junctions.

DISCUSSION

We present OCT vibrometry measurements of cochlear partition structures *in situ* from a fresh human specimen with a healthy-looking organ of Corti. Sound-driven motion of cochlear partition structures between the scala tympani surface to the scala vestibuli surface, such as OSL, bridge, BM, RL, and TM were measured. These results indicate that the OSL moved considerably in relation to the stapes input. However, the OSL displacement was 20 dB less than the peak of the BM displacement. As a comparison, measurements of BM displacement were about 16 dB higher than the OSL in guinea pig [9], and the BM moved 15 dB more than the “bony limbus” in squirrel monkey [10]. These previous *in vivo* measurements in two different species have similar BM/OSL motion ratios as reported here in a healthy human cadaveric temporal bone.

Compared to the BM, the RL and TM generally moved similarly and in phase. However, the BM had slightly larger displacements. In two ears with pathological or missing organs of Corti, the cochlear partition motion differed from the ear presented here and other ears with healthy-appearing organs of Corti (not shown).

We report vibrometry data of the cochlear partition in the transverse direction (perpendicular to the BM). Future measurements will include measurements from multiple angles to reconstruct radial motions to determine shearing motions between the RL and TM due to BM motion.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

Chris Bergevin: Were you able to do any sort of fixation and histology after your experiments to get a better sense for what the structures of everything look like, and then relate that back to the mechanical measurements?

Paul Secchia: We are actively doing that right now and have been since the beginning of our experiments. Histology can take up to two years, so some of the ears that we did at the very beginning are just now in the final stages of processing. We are also collaborating with friends in the Otopathology lab over at Mass. Eye and Ear to work on a novel histological technique that has a more rapid time scale. For every single ear we have imaged, the contralateral ear is processed for histology, and we are collecting that histology data to better understand our OCT measurements.

Stefan Stenfelt: When I did similar measurements a long time ago, looking at the OSL, I saw more of a bending motion on it. In these graphs, I only saw more of a single motion. Is that because you are only looking at the tip of the OSL, or am I missing something?

Paul Secchia: You saw that right. When looking through the intact round window, we are often able to only visualize 25% of the total length of the OSL, and in some cases we have been able to open it up and extend our measurements further. We are familiar with your data and have talked about it a lot in our group, and it matches pretty closely to our “small organ of Corti” ears, which makes sense because your experiments were 6 days postmortem as opposed to being very fresh. Your data included more of the total length of the OSL, but we were happy that we were able to reproduce your data at the tip of the OSL.

Tao Cheng: The “larger organ of Corti” versus “smaller organ of Corti” does not mean it is healthy or nonhealthy. Some cochleae just have a larger organ of Corti, some have smaller ones. Have you done anything to rule out if those cochleae are normal versus nonnormal? For instance, Heidi you said measure the phase of the stapes, and check the round window and oval window for air bubbles, and other things like that.

Paul Secchia: We are hoping to figure that out in our ongoing histology project. And these measurements are all from a similar longitudinal region within a 2 mm range, where we believe the organ of Corti should be a comparable size. Of course, individual variation is a potential concern, but we are hoping to understand and rule that possibility out once we have the histology for each ear.

Tao Cheng (cont.): Do you check the cochlea for air bubbles?

Paul Secchia: We do check for air bubbles. We also do a visual inspection of the middle ear and will test the round window reflex when measuring stapes velocity to ensure that sound transmission into the inner ear is normal.

Susan Voss: Do you have a sense when postmortem changes might start to kick in? I am also assuming that you are using temporal bone plugs for your experiments?

Paul Secchia: Yes we are.

Susan Voss (cont.): Having made temporal bone measurements, I understand the need for using plugs, but is it possible to do the same experiment in a whole head to show that you get the same thing? Is it worth it?

Paul Secchia: Whole head experiments are certainly possible, and a bit more expensive as we are competing with other researchers (especially the brain ones) for fresh human specimens. To answer your question on postmortem degradation, Nam Hyun Cho, Haobing Wang, and Sunil Puria have written a good paper on postmortem changes observed with OCT in gerbils where they saw that there can be massive postmortem changes—especially in the fluid spaces—within the first half-hour to hour after death. From histology though, the standard “textbook” view from Schuknecht’s Pathology of the Ear and our Otopath lab collaborators says that postmortem autolytic changes start to be very pronounced around the 30 hour mark. I have only presented data from 5 ears here, but we have imaged around 30-40 fresh ears in my 3 years as a graduate student, and the magic number I have seen is 35 hours postmortem. In my experience, anything over 35 hours postmortem will look poor and have this swollen balloon-like appearance. I

have done some statistics in a different project where we see a small but significant change in the size of the organ of Corti in ears with postmortem times greater than 24 hours. For this set of data, one of our ears was 30 hours postmortem, but the others were 12, 13, 16, and 23 hours postmortem, which are pretty typical postmortem times for specimens in a temporal bone library.